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A Preliminary Evaluation of Bamboo Tree Effect on Selected Properties of Coal Spoil Contaminated Soils of a Humid Area of Southern Nigeria

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Abstract

Coal exploitation produces an overburden mine spoil that overtime contaminates the soil environment. This study was conducted to evaluate the effect of Giant bamboo (*Dendrocalamus giganteus*) tree species on selected properties of overburden coal spoil contaminated soil. The treatment consisted of arable and agroforestry land soils contaminated with overburden coal spoil in the ratio of 1:1 (W/W) and the overburden coal spoil laid out in a completely randomized design (CRD) in five replications. Data was collected from the recombinant treatments of planted Giant bamboo cuttings in each of the treatment on the soil properties and growth response of the plants at 30, 60, 90 and 120 days respectively after shooting and were subjected to ANOVA while significant means to LSD. Results showed that the soil pH, Organic concentration, Total Nitrogen, bio available, Pb, Cd, Fe, Zn, Bulk density and total porosity differed significantly ($P=0.05$). There was a consistent increase in organic C content across the treatments between 30 and 120 days after shooting. Relative to the pre-bamboo planting values, bio available Pb and Cd across treatments decreased as the days after bamboo shooting increased but decreased between 30 and 120 days by Pb (31.96%) and Cd (9.90%) respectively. Similarly, the bulk density declined while the total porosity increased with increase in the number of days after shooting in the order agroforestry > arable > coal spoil soils to underpin better bamboo growth performance with the recombinant agroforestry soil, relative to the other treatments. These suggest that the bamboo did not only improve the soil physical characteristics but also removed some heavy metals (Pb and Cd) from the soil. Hence the plant could be a suitable phytoremediation plant for the restoration of coal mine degraded lands.

Keyword: Recombinant Treatment, Agroforestry and Arable Land Soils, Bio available, Trace elements, Bulk density, Total Porosity

1. Introduction

Coal is amongst the non-renewable energy sources in Nigeria with its exploration and exploitation dated back to 1909 and 1905 respectively, although the utilization dropped after the civil war due to the diversion to crude oil (Ogunsola, 1991). However, recent economic realities which demand for export diversification and improved power generation have renewed the interest of Nigerian government in revitalizing the coal mining industry (Oceri *et al.*, 2017) with increasing search for the deposits across the country irrespective of the commercial quantity. Furthermore, the existing potential market for coal briquetted remains an attraction and a probable compliment for fuel wood, amidst global deforestation crisis with a view to reducing deforestation and its component impacts on ground water degradation and climate change.

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Coal occur in more than six states of the country, these include, Anambra, Benue, Delta, Enugu and Nasarawa (Abalaka and Aga, 2016) that are well known for food production potentials which could be adversely affected by mining and thus undermine contribution to economic growth and environmental sustainability. The process of coal mining results in a lot of waste which include over – burden coal spoil materials that lies above an area that lend itself to economic exploitation such as rock soil and ecosystem that lies above a coal seam). This waste constitutes environmental hazards with high potential of soil damage (Ghose, 2005), alteration of microorganism community and decimation of existing vegetation (Adeyinka and Bankole, 2019). Sigh and Seem (2017) reported that overburden coal spoil produced during mining resulted in elevated bio availability of heavy metals, sand content, lack of moisture, increased compaction and relatively low organic matter in soil. Consequently, these adversely affect the biological diversity within the micro-environment and need to be ameliorated in a sustainable manner.

Giant Bamboo (*Dendrocalamus giganteus*) is among the fastest growing grass spp. It is an important non-timber forest product (NTFP) that has been described by Effah *et al.* (2014) as a valuable asset for environmental conservation and land rehabilitation There are several reports (Zhou *et al.*, 2005, Lobovikov *et al.*, 2009, Shoel *et al.*, 2015) on different forms of ecosystem goods and services associated with bamboo-based land use systems. Jacob *et al.*, (2015) and Paudyal *et al.*, (2017) reported the role bamboo in Global Restoration Program Targets, aimed at rehabilitating 150 million ha of degraded land by 2020 and the New York Declaration on Forest, aimed at restoring 350 million ha by 2030. Emamverdian *et al.* (2018), extensively reviewed the phytoremediation potentials of plants. High biomass production, fast growing rate, wide rooting system and tolerance to abiotic stress are the outstanding characteristics that make bamboo trees species suitable phytoremediation plant.

In rural setting of Nigeria, Bamboo tree species is an important component of the farming system, especially in marginal lands were the significantly high litter fall contribute to soil nutrient restoration capacity (Egwanatum, *et al.*, 2020). The plant which severe as building material, fuel wood as well as economic resource for the rural poor has remained a minor forest produce with a multifunctional forest regime. Despite all these potential roles, there is paucity of information on the ameliorative effect of bamboo on contaminated soils in the humid area of Nigeria. The objective of the study was to evaluate the effect of bamboo tree species on coal spoil contaminated soils as a phytoremediation plant for the sustainable agricultural practices amidst coal exploitation activities at Ukwu-Nzu, Delta State, in the already pollution stressed Niger Delta region of Nigeria..

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Description of study area

The study was carried out at Uku-Nzu, Aniocha North Local Government Area of Delta State as a pot experiment. Uku – Nzu lies between Lat. 06° 23' and 06° 25'N and Long. 06° 30' and 06° 35'E. The climate is humid tropics with a mean annual rainfall of 1500mm of which 75% is received during the months of June and July. Average annual temperature of the location is between 28 and 32°C, while the relative humidity is over 77.3% on the average annually (NiMet, 2017).

The soil is derived from the coastal plain sand, characterized by deep porous loamy sand surface overlying clayey loam sub soil (FORMECU, 2000). The community is at present the only location in Delta State with ascertained commercial quantity of coal, lignite and kaolin. This has attracted no small attention for prospective commercial exploitation against the localized ongoing exploitation with various agreement reached between the community the Federal Government of Nigeria as these mineral resources are on the exclusive list of the Nigerian Constitution. However, the Delta State Government currently manages the local use through the Ministry of Commerce and Industry with no attendant concern on the emanating impact on the environment, especially the decimation of its waste spoil soil on the scarce agricultural land in the Ukwu-Nzu community.

2.2 Experimental Layout

Soils from two land use types (Arable and Agroforestry) were contaminated with overburden coal spoil at ratio 1:1 (W/W) as treatments and the overburden coal spoil as control. All were taken at the depth of 0-40cm from the same location then air dried and sieved before recharging in poly pots at 10 per treatment. The arable land consists of 2years old cassava/maize mixture without fertilizer of any type, while the agroforestry-land was bamboo/cassava/maize mixture of the same age. The experiment was arranged in a Completely Randomized Design in five replicates and watered to equilibrate with the micro-climatic condition of the temporary nursery.

Bamboo cuttings of the same stock were sourced for planting. Each had four (4) nodes and one of the four nodes was pushed into the soil, leaving the other three above the surface for the monitoring of the plant growth response. Three cuttings were planted per pot containing 5kg of the treatments and later thinned to one at two weeks after planting to constitute the recombinant treatments. The pots containing the plants were raised on a platform (>60cm height) and uniformly watered with 1litre of water every other day for 10days.

2.3 Data Collection and Analysis

Prior to the contamination, soil samples were taken from the arable and agroforestry lands and the coal spoil for the determination of selected physicochemical properties. At 30, 60, 90 and 120 days after shooting respectively, soil samples were taken from each of the treatments across the replicates.

The samples were air dried at room temperature, crushed and passed through 2mm sieve mesh. Except for the bulk density and total porosity determination which were restricted to pre-planting sample, all the samples were analyzed for total N, Organic C, pH (H₂O) and available P (Bray -1) using ITTA (1989) procedure and bioavailable Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd using the method described by Kucak and Blanus (1998).

Data on the plant response to the treatments were based on number shoots on each node position (upper, middle and lower) from the planting surface and the leaf area at each node position. These were measured at 30, 60, 90 and 120 days after shooting. The leaf area was determined based on Obi (1991) description.

Data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the procedure for CRD. Significant means were separated using the Least Significant Difference (LSD) approach at 5% level of probability.

3. Result and Discussion

Table 1 shows some physico-chemical properties of the soils (arable and agroforestry) prior to contamination and the contaminant (coal mine soil spoil). Generally, the soils were acid in reaction, with the coal mine spoil having the lowest pH (4.50).

The organic C, total N and available P in the agroforestry soil were higher than those of the arable land soil and coal mine spoil in that order. The values of these biogenic nutrients in the arable and agroforestry land soils were significantly higher than those of the coal mine spoil. These could be as a result of nonexistence of any vegetation on the overburden coal soil. Vegetation is the major source of soil organic C and total nitrogen. This is in line with the report of Ghose (2005), who observed that overburden coal spoil soils are often characterized by low organic matter and total N content. Similarly, the observed low pH of the overburden coal spoil soil is in agreement with report of Adeyinka and Bankole (2019) on such materials within Enugu area of south eastern Nigeria.

For the bioavailable form of Pb and Cd, the value recorded from the overburden coal spoil were significantly higher ($P \geq 0.05$) than those of the arable and forest land soils. The concentration of bioavailable Fe followed the same trend, with the value recorded from the overburden coal spoil being 57.89% and 22.98% higher than that of agroforestry and arable land soils, respectively. However, the concentration of bioavailable Zn in the

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agroforestry and arable land soils was significantly higher than that of overburden coal spoil. The observed higher concentration of bioavailable forms of Pb, Cd and Fe could be attributed to the low pH.

Sigh and Seema (2017) and Adeyinka and Bankole (2019) made similar observation over coal mine spoil soil in different locations. Similarly, Bhyiyan *et al.* (2010) reported that several layers located upon coal bed contain a lot of Fe and other heavy metal (trace elements) compared to an adjacent native soil.

Higher bulk density which reflects higher degree of compaction was observed in overburden coal spoil soil relative to the two other soils. This was followed by reversed values in total porosity. Madegon *et al.*, (2006) made similar observation and reported that an overburden coal spoil was characterized by increased compaction and lack of moisture despite an elevated sand content.

3.1 Effect of the Bamboo on selected physicochemical properties of the contaminated soils and the contaminant.

As shown in Table 2, from 30 to 120 days after shooting, the bamboo effect on the physicochemical characteristics of the contaminated soils and contaminants differed significantly. At 30days after shooting, the values of organic C, total N and bioavailable Zn as well as total porosity recorded from the contaminated soil were significantly higher than those of the contaminants and their respective initial values before bamboo planting. However, the pH, available P and bioavailable Cd contents did not differ significantly but higher concentration of bioavailable Pb and lower pH were recorded from the contaminants. Compared to their initial values (before planting) the amount of Cd and Pb in the contaminated soils and contaminants were significantly lower at 30days after planting.

The results at 60, 90 and 120 days after shooting, follow similar trend as those the 30day after planting with the pH value being significantly lower in the contaminants.

The organic C increased progressively from the 30th day after shooting up to the 120th day. However, the reverse was the case for total N, with values obtained between 60 and 90 days after shooting being lower than those of the 30days after shooting. Available P declined with age of the bamboo tree species with an increase in organic matter, organic carbon but decrease in total N.

The progressive (although gradually) increase in organic C from 30 – 120 days after shooting compared to slight decrease in total N, available P and bioavailable Zn could be as a result of root activities associated early development of the bamboo which is commonly observed during early stage plant growth on soil (Okore *et al.*, 2006).

Physical characteristics of the soil measured (bulk density and total porosity) showed an improvement with age of the bamboo across the treatments. Between 30 to 60 days after shoot, the bulk density did not differ significantly across the treatments, however at 90 and 120 days after shooting, the agroforestry and arable land soils (contaminated) had significantly low values compared to over burden coal spoil. Generally, the bulk density decreased progressively with the age of the bamboo, with increase in the total porosity.

This could be ascribed to the dense and fibrous rooting nature of bamboo tree species as reported by Emamverdian *et al.* (2018). Similarly, Singh and Seema (2017) reported that planting fibrous rooted plants such as bamboo and other grasses could improve soil physical characteristics such as compaction and drainage.

On the bioavailable trace elements, the concentration of Pb and Cd decreased progressively from the 30th to the 120th day after bamboo shooting, irrespective of the treatment. However, significantly lower values were recorded from the contaminated arable and agroforestry soils compared to the contaminant coal soil.

Relative to the values recorded from the pre bamboo planting samples, the concentration of Fe, Pb and Cd decreased considerably with the age of the bamboo on the soils. The potential ability of plant species such as

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bamboo in detoxifying heavy metal contaminated soils has been reported by Rajkumar *et al.* (2010) and Emamverdian *et al.* (2018)

3.2 Growth Response of the Bamboo to Contaminated Soils and the Contaminant

The growth response of the bamboo to the contaminated soils and the contaminants as reflected by the leaf area and number of buds at different node position is presented in Table 3. The result shows that irrespective of the treatment, the node position closer to the soil surface (lower node) consistently had higher number of buds between 30 and 120 days after shooting.

Amongst the treatment, contaminated agroforestry and arable soils significantly produced more buds compared to overburden coal spoils. Furthermore, the agroforestry soil demonstrated higher capacity to support the growth response of Bamboo compared to the arable soil. The budding potential maintained the same trend at 30 and 60 days after shooting while that at 90 and 120 days followed the same pattern. Data on the leaf area followed similar trend with plants in the contaminated agroforestry soil having wider leaves relative to the other treatments. Bamboo trees tolerance of abiotic stress such as hazardous waste contamination is reported by Yan *et al.* (2015)

4. Conclusion

The results of this study suggest that over burden coal spoils are contaminants that can be decontaminated for environmental safety. Planting of bamboo could result in gradual improvement in the bulk density and total porosity which are critical to the further land use implication of coal spoil contaminated soil. Also, low pH of the soil which may have triggered an increase in the concentration of bioavailable trace elements such as Pb, Cd and Fe in the overburden coal spoil contaminated soil, could be phyto-remediated with recombinant bamboo tree species-agroforestry land use soil which demonstrated better phytoremediation properties than the rather spent arable land use soil. However, the need for further studies on the effect of bamboo plant on biogenic nutrients (N and P) and the average number of recombinant bamboo tree species-agroforestry land use soil required in the phytoremediation of different hectares of coal spoil soils cannot be overemphasized.

Table 1: Selected physicochemical properties of the contaminated arable, agroforestry and the overburden coal spoils soils prior to the bamboo plantings.

Selected Physicochemical properties	pH (H ₂ O)	Org C g/kg	Total N g/kg	AV.P mg/kg	Pb mg/kg	Cd mg/kg	Zn mg/kg	Fe mg/kg	Total Porosity (%)	Bulk Density (g/cm ³)
Arable land soil	4.7	4.3	0.45	4.2	4.76	1.21	6.88	30.45	28.32	1.84
Agroforestry land soil	5.1	6.1	0.75	8.14	3.2	1.05	8.8	48.62	37.1	1.71
Overburden coal spoil soil	4.5	1.18	0.23	3.11	6.86	2.68	4.52	71.6	18.2	1.92
LSD (0.05)	Ns	2.14	0.09	0.92	1.03	0.21	2.48	11.92	6.14	0.06

Av,P= Bray-1 Available Phosphorus Ns = Not Significant

Table 2: Effect of Bamboo tree on physicochemical properties of coal spoil contaminated soils between 30 and 120 days after shooting

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Growth period (Days)	Types of contaminated soil	Selected Chemical Properties									
		pH (H ₂ O)	Org C.	Total N	Avail P	Zn	Fe	Pb	Cd	Bulk Density	Total Porosity
		mg/kg	mg/kg	mg/kg	mg/kg	mg/kg	mg/kg	mg/kg	g/kg	(gcm ⁻³)	(%)
30	Arable Land	4.73	7.14	0.45	3.83	6.83	50.1	5.72	1.05	1.84	28.45
	Agroforestry land	5.5	12.5	0.71	7.2	8.6	65.1	4.13	1.01	1.75	37.46
	Coal Mine Spoil	4.64	3	0.32	3.8	4.52	71.3	6.84	1.66	1.86	18.52
	LSD (0.05)	NS	2.61	0.08	NS	3.11	15.01	NS	0.04	NS	5.54
60	Arable Land	4.97	7.22	0.4	3.63	6.8	49.27	5.46	1.14	1.8	18.65
	Agroforestry land	5.8	12.8	0.68	7.12	8.53	63.28	4.01	1.02	1.73	37.39
	Coal Mine Spoil	4.7	3.5	0.31	3.64	4.52	70.4	6.76	1.64	1.8	18.65
	LSD (0.05)	0.45	5.02	0.08	NS	3.02	18.12	0.61	0.11	NS	12.6
90	Arable Land	5.9	7.84	0.42	3.4	6.53	49.25	5.12	1.11	1.52	29.1
	Agroforestry land	6.1	13.1	0.67	6.87	8.34	63.22	3.78	1.12	1.56	38.28
	Coal Mine Spoil	4.8	3.58	0.3	3.34	4.4	69.1	6.53	1.62	1.78	19.3
	LSD (0.05)	1.04	4.29	0.11	0.95	2.24	16.34	1.2	0.05	0.13	10.2
120	Arable Land	5.8	8.2	0.5	3.25	6.44	48.38	4.84	1.02	1.5	19.25
	Agroforestry land	6.4	13.12	0.73	6.83	8.1	61.4	2.81	0.91	1.55	39.58
	Coal Mine Spoil	4.9	4.08	0.38	3.34	4.3	68.6	6.31	1.58	1.61	19.25
	LSD (0.05)	0.04	3.34	0.09	1.02	2.64	15.66	2.41	0.16	0.44	6.32

3: Growth responses of bamboo stump to coal spoil contamination between 30 and 120 days after shooting

Growth period (Days)	Types of contaminated soil	Mean no. of buds per node Nodal Positions			Mean leaf area per node Nodal Positions (cm ²)		
		Lower	Middle	Upper	Lower	Middle	Upper
30	Arable Land	2	1	1	2.36	1.25	1.15
	Agroforestry land	4	3	1	9.9	7.62	7.35
	Coal Mine Spoil	1	1	1	0.32	0.55	0.2
	LSD (0.05)	1.56	NS	NS	5.16	4.11	3.91

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60	Arable Land	3	1	1	5.7	7.1	2.1
	Agroforestry land	7	3	2	8.87	14.06	4.73
	Coal Mine Spoil	1	1	1	0.84	0.68	0.53
	LSD (0.05)	2.14	NS	NS	4.42	5.24	1.92
90	Arable Land	3	2	2	8.5	10.1	5.4
	Agroforestry land	10	5	2	15.04	17.12	12.36
	Coal Mine Spoil	2	2	1	4.05	6.23	2.13
	LSD (0.05)	6.2	0.48	NS	8.14	6.16	7.74
120	Arable Land	5	2	2	16.95	13.81	9.15
	Agroforestry land	13	8	3	22.68	24.65	17.92
	Coal Mine Spoil	3	2	1	7.41	7.01	3.11
	LSD (0.05)	5.6	3.8	NS	7.24	8.61	5.09

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